

Low-Rank Modal Decomposition of Beat-Resolved Retinal Laser Doppler Holography at 37,000 Frames per Second Reveals Flicker-Evoked Arterial Neurovascular Signatures

Lancelot Doucet,¹ David Gouyoumdjian,¹ Maxime Boy Arnould,¹ Yann Fischer,¹ Zacharie Auray,¹ and Michael Atlan^{1,*}

¹Institut Langevin, CNRS, ESPCI Paris, PSL University, Paris, France

*michael.atlan@cnrs.fr

Abstract: Beat-resolved retinal Doppler holography yields synchronized blood velocity arterial/venous waveforms in seconds. A per-acquisition low-rank modal decomposition extracts a canonical pulse template and a residual fraction. During 13 Hz flicker, canonical pulsatile strength decreases while residual heterogeneity increases.

1. Motivation

Retinal neurovascular coupling provides a noninvasive functional assay of microvascular regulation: a brief visual stimulus can evoke rapid adjustments of vascular tone and flow linked to metabolic demand signaling. Mean-flow surrogates can miss stimulus-driven changes in heterogeneous responses across the vascular tree. Beat-resolved retinal laser Doppler holography provides an information-rich alternative: within a seconds-long, dye-free recording, it delivers synchronous arterial and venous velocity waveforms over many vessel segments and beats. We introduce a low-rank decomposition framework that separates a shared arterial pulsatile component from residual structure within each acquisition. The goal is to produce within-acquisition endpoints that (a) quantify how strongly a dominant canonical pulse template is expressed and (b) quantify how much pulsatile content is not captured by that dominant mode. This combination is designed to distinguish “less pulsation overall” from “more heterogeneous or more complex pulsation,” two scenarios that can be conflated by average-only analyses.

2. Ultrahigh-speed digital holography device

The instrument is based on an inline Mach–Zehnder interferometer operating at $\lambda = 852$ nm. The laser beam is split into an illumination arm ($\sim 90\%$) and a reference arm ($\sim 10\%$) using polarization-maintaining fibers. In the illumination arm, the beam is diffused by an engineered diffuser and delivered to the eye in a diffuse Maxwellian-view configuration. The eyepiece is implemented as two biconvex lenses with an effective focal length of ~ 33 mm to form a wide-field illumination/collection geometry. Cross-polarized backscattered light from the fundus is recombined with the reference beam to form interferograms encoding Doppler fluctuations from moving blood cells. Image rendering and analysis yields local velocity waveforms $v(t, x, y)$, aggregated in beats (b), and averaged across vessel segment branches (k) and distance (r) from the optic disc, yielding $v(t, b, k, r)$.

3. Dataset and stimulation epochs

We illustrate the approach on the dataset from an experiment organized into three successive epochs across acquisitions: Baseline 1 (acq 0–6), Flicker (13 Hz white led light ~ 0.2 mW) (acq 7–18), and Baseline 2 (acq 19–27). For each acquisition, the data provide beat-aligned segment waveforms $v(t, b, k, r)$, where t indexes within-beat samples (all waveforms are linearly interpolated to the same number of time points within each period), b indexes beats, and (k, r) indexes vessel location (branch and radial coordinate). A binary mask indicates valid (b, k, r) entries. Throughout, each acquisition is summarized as one statistical unit (one dot per acquisition) using robust aggregation over valid entries: dots report medians across vessel locations and beats, while whiskers quantify within-acquisition beat-to-beat dispersion after spatial aggregation.

Fig. 1: Canonical pulsatile amplitude (Mode-1 strength) and Mode-1 residual fraction.

4. Per-acquisition low-rank decomposition and analysis

For each beat and location we remove the local temporal mean, $\mu(b, k, r) = \langle v(t, b, k, r) \rangle_t$, so that $v - \mu$ emphasizes pulsatile structure rather than absolute offset. Within each acquisition, we stack valid mean-removed waveforms into a 2D matrix $X(:, j) = v(\cdot, b, k, r) - \mu(b, k, r)$ where j indexes b, k, r . We compute the singular value decomposition (SVD), $X = U\Sigma V^\top$, and define the dominant temporal mode $u_1(t) = U(:, 1)$ (canonical pulse shape for that acquisition). The Mode-1 scores are $a_1(b, k, r) \leftrightarrow s_1 \tilde{v}_1(j)$, where $s_1 = \Sigma_{11}$ and $\tilde{v}_1 = V(:, 1)$. This yields the rank-1 approximation $v(t, b, k, r) = \mu(b, k, r) + a_1(b, k, r)u_1(t) + \varepsilon(t, b, k, r)$. Because SVD is sign-indeterminate, we fix the sign within each acquisition by a deterministic convention: if $\text{median}_{b, k, r}(a_1) < 0$, set $(u_1, a_1) \leftarrow (-u_1, -a_1)$. This does not change reconstructions but ensures consistent orientation across acquisitions.

We quantify the typical strength of the canonical pulsation using a within-beat $\text{RMS}_t(x) = \sqrt{\langle x(t)^2 \rangle_t}$ and define

$$A_1 = \text{median}_{b, k, r} \left(\text{RMS}_t(a_1 u_1) \right), \quad (1)$$

with beat-to-beat dispersion $\sigma_{A_1, \text{beat}} = \text{std}_b \left(\text{median}_{k, r}(\text{RMS}_t(a_1 u_1)) \right)$. We report a dimensionless Mode-1 residual fraction

$$\rho_1 = \frac{\text{median}_{b, k, r} \text{RMS}_t[v - \mu - a_1 u_1]}{\text{median}_{b, k, r} \text{RMS}_t[v - \mu]}. \quad (2)$$

Interpreted as an *unexplained pulsatile proportion*, larger ρ_1 indicates that a single canonical template captures a smaller share of pulsatile structure (consistent with increased spatial heterogeneity, beat-to-beat morphology variability, and/or stronger higher-order modes). Because it is normalized within acquisition, ρ_1 is less sensitive to global scaling than absolute-amplitude measures, but it can increase if measurement quality degrades (motion, SNR loss, alignment errors, or changes in valid coverage). Reporting basic QC covariates alongside ρ_1 (valid fraction, motion score, signal-to-noise ratio,...) should be done in the next studies.

5. Results: a coupled flicker signature

In the reported experiment, flicker induces a consistent coupled pattern at the per-acquisition level: (i) Canonical pulsatile strength decreases: A_1 shifts downward during 13 Hz flicker relative to both baseline epochs. (ii) Residual heterogeneity increases: ρ_1 shifts upward during flicker, indicating that the dominant canonical template explains a smaller fraction of the pulsatile content. This joint behavior is informative because it separates amplitude modulation from redistribution toward complexity: a decrease in A_1 alone could reflect uniformly weaker pulsations, whereas an increase in ρ_1 indicates a larger share of pulsatile structure outside the dominant template, consistent with heterogeneous segment-level responses and/or altered waveform morphology not captured by a single mode.

6. Conclusion

Low-rank modal decomposition of beat-resolved retinal Doppler holography isolates a dominant canonical arterial pulse template and a normalized residual fraction. In a 13 Hz flicker light stimulation experiment in a healthy volunteer, canonical pulsatile strength decreases while residual heterogeneity increases, revealing a neurovascular signature that can be muted or missed by mean-only summaries. This framework provides compact within-session endpoints for functional microvascular phenotyping.